

**DIFFICULTIES OF TRANSLATING CLOTHING NAMES IN UZBEK
AND ENGLISH**

Hamroyeva Mukhlisa Farkhod qizi

Muhlisakhamroyeva@gmail.com

TerDPI, Languages faculty

ABSTRACT

This article examines the difficulties in translating clothing names in Uzbek and English languages. In translation linguistics, the process of translating cultural lexical units, in particular clothing terms, is a complex process depending on various cultural differences and national dress traditions. The article discusses cultural differences, the influence of climate and geographical conditions, and national and semantic differences in clothing names as the main difficulties. Ways to overcome these problems are presented through descriptive translation and cultural equivalents.

Keywords: translation difficulties, cultural differences, clothing names, Uzbek language, French language, national dress, semantic differences, descriptive translation, translation strategies.

**ТРУДНОСТИ ПЕРЕВОДА НАЗВАНИЙ ОДЕЖДЫ НА УЗБЕКСКИЙ И
АНГЛИЙСКИЙ ЯЗЫКИ**

АННОТАЦИЯ

В данной статье рассматриваются трудности перевода названий одежды с узбекского и английского языков. В лингвистике перевода процесс перевода культурных лексических единиц, в частности терминов одежды, представляет собой сложный процесс, обусловленный различными культурными различиями и национальными традициями одежды. В статье рассматриваются культурные различия, влияние климата и географических условий, а также национально-смысловые различия названий одежды как основные трудности. Пути решения этих проблем представлены посредством описательного перевода и культурных эквивалентов.

Ключевые слова: трудности перевода, культурные различия, названия одежды, узбекский язык, французский язык, национальная одежда, семантические различия, описательный перевод, стратегии перевода.

INTRODUCTION

In translation linguistics cultural lexical units, in particular, the translation of clothing names, in many cases cause great difficulties. These difficulties are mainly related to the specific differences between the language and culture of the two nations. This article analyzes the main problems encountered in the translation of clothing names from Uzbek and English languages, including cultural differences, national dress styles, and the influence of climate on translation.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

For this article, comparative, literary, descriptive translation and explanatory analysis of linguistic terms, stylistic analysis of literature was considered during the research. The difficulties of translating the names of clothing in Uzbek and English languages were studied taking into account cultural differences, semantic ambiguity of words, climatic and geographical conditions, and national clothing styles. The main difficulties encountered in the process of translation were analyzed and practical examples were presented with the help of scientific literature. During the research on this article, scientific analyzes such as Saidov M- cultural lexical units in Uzbek and foreign languages, Bakhodirov Sh- Translation theory and practice, Kamoljonovich.S.J- Linguistic-perspective problems of anthroponyms in JK Rowling's fantastic works were studied.

RESULTS

The main difficulties in translating the names of clothing in Uzbek and English are related to cultural, climatic and historical factors. Cultural differences between the Uzbek and British nations have a significant impact on the terminology of clothing. Methods such as descriptive translation and explaining the cultural context can be used to overcome translation difficulties.

DISCUSSION

Cultural differences and national dress styles. There is a big difference between the national costumes of the Uzbek and British nations. Therefore, the cultural differences between Uzbek and English national clothes are important in finding an exact equivalent when translating the names of clothes. Since the Uzbek word "chopon" does not have an exact equivalent in English, it should be translated as "Uzbek chapan" or "Uzbek traditional robe" as a national outerwear. However, this translation cannot fully express the unique cultural characteristics of the word chapon. Also, it is a bit difficult to find the correct English equivalent for the Uzbek "to'n" dress. Therefore, it is translated as "Uzbek traditional coat" or "Uzbek robe".

Uzbek and British nationalities are distinguished by their traditional aspects of clothing culture. Uzbek national clothes are mainly made of cotton and silk, traditional clothes include capes, caps, satin and adras dresses. English fashion mainly expresses its uniqueness through clothes such as hats, morning suits, tail coats, tuxedos, corsages, and kilts. Therefore, it is sometimes difficult to find the correct equivalent when translating these costumes.

There are difficulties in translation and non-traditional usage. Some clothing names, such as the Uzbek "do'ppi" and the English "skullcap", are culturally specific and may not have the correct equivalent in translation. Their national cultural meanings and social context should be taken into account in the translation.

There are Influence of climate and geographical factors. Sometimes, when it is not possible to directly translate the names of clothes, their descriptive translation is done. In this way, the clothes being translated are explained to the reader by describing them. This is done through a description method based on the shape, material and function of the garments. For example, when translating the word "kovush" in Uzbek, it is used as a description like "slippers". In English, since this type of shoes is not widespread, a description is used to make it understandable to an English reader.

Also, there are many idioms which are used from clothing names. Such expressions are hundreds of years old, their original connection with clothing has already been erased, so they are difficult to understand and remember. **We have selected idioms for clothes, pants, shirt, shoes and other items of clothing. To make them easier to remember, we talk about their origin, literal meaning, interesting facts and ways of using them in speech. I'd eat my hat and swallow the buckle whole.** "I'll eat my hat and swallow the clasp. **Below the belt** - unfair, dishonest. Literally – "**below the belt.**" The origin of the phrase is not difficult to guess. This idiom is similar to the Russian expression "low blow", so it's easy to remember. In this case, the English expression does not need to use the word "strike", for example: Your attitude to my wedding is below the belt. "Your treatment of my wedding is unfair. **Old hat** - an outdated, unfashionable thing. "**Old hat**" - this is what they say not only about clothes, but also about other things: appliances, furniture, jewelry. This can also be said about people - for example, the elderly or those with outdated views. Old hat is synonymous with out of fashion. A phrase with this meaning appeared in English at the beginning of the 20th century. Interestingly, in the old version of English, the phrase old hat had a much more vulgar meaning.

With hat in hand - humbly, servilely, obsequiously

The expression “With a hat in hand” refers to the times when the British wore hats. The hat was removed from the head and held in the hands as a sign of respect. Now this gesture is no longer used, but the phrase has been preserved in the language. So often they say about asking people. In the sentence, the phrase with hat in hand serves as an introductory construction.

Keep your shirt on / keep your pants on - keep calm. When unflappable English people ask you not to lose your temper, they literally say “do not take off your shirt or trousers”. This idiom is often used to calm nervous, agitated people.

CONCLUSION

We face many difficulties in translating the names of clothes in Uzbek and English languages. The reasons for this are mainly cultural differences, idioms, historical and social factors, as well as the fact that each language and culture have their own terminological systems. In order to correctly translate these terms, the translator must not only have excellent knowledge of two languages, but also a deep understanding of the cultural context in order to be able to describe the words.

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